

Internal Control, External Audit and Earnings Management: Evidence from Chinese Listed Companies

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Abstract

Based on the panel data of China's A-share listed companies from 2013 to 2017, this paper divided earnings management (EM) into accrual and real earnings management and studied how internal control (IC) and external audit, the two internal and external governance mechanisms, affect the two types of earnings management. A sample size of 12,392 value observations was drawn from 2,939 research enterprises. Earnings management model, as well as multiple linear regression models, were used to analyze the data collected. The empirical results show that, both internal control and external audit can directly restrain the enterprise's accrual earnings management, while internal control is ineffective on real earnings management, an external audit can still be effective on real earnings management. Internal control and external audit have complementary relationships in regulating accrual earnings management, while there is neither substitution nor complementary relationship in regulating real earnings management.

Keywords: Internal Control; External Audit; Accrual Earnings Management, Real Earnings Management

1. Introduction

Due to the universality, legitimacy, secrecy and the non-reality of removing earnings management (EM) (Yang Shunhua, 2010), scholars always focus on researching EM, which can be divided into two categories: real earnings management and accrual earnings management. In the past, the research on earnings management mostly concentrated on accrual earnings management. However, since Roychowhury (2006) and Cohen et al. (2008) and so on, scholars begin to carry out research from the accrual earnings management to real earnings management activities, which made the academic research more in line with actual business practice. However, another question that arises is what can effectively regulate the accrual and real earnings management behavior of an enterprise. Since the Enron incident, the United States of American enacts SOX Act and requires listed companies to strengthen internal control in order to regulate earnings management and improve the quality of accounting reports. Since then, scholars begin to study the relationship between internal control and earnings management and find that effective internal control can indeed regulate earnings management behavior of enterprises. At the same time, with the enactment of the SOX Act, most companies have changed the way of earnings management from accrual earnings management to real earnings management with more secrecy. In recent years, some scholars have proposed external audit, as a kind of external governance mechanism, which can effectively regulate earnings management behavior of enterprises. Many scholars have proved that companies audited by the Big four International Accounting Firms (International BIG4) have lower motivation and level of earnings management through empirical research. Gong Qihui (2015) argues that the choice of accrual and real earnings management is the result of careful consideration based on the internal and external environment and there is a substitution relationship between accrual and real earnings management modes. How do internal control and external audit have a combined effect on earnings management in the enterprise? The few kinds of literature in China basically use the data before the implementation of the Guidelines for the Application of Enterprise Internal Control (GAEIC) by listed companies in China, and no consistent conclusion

has been reached to date. So, how will these two governance mechanisms affect earnings management after the mandatory implementation of the guidelines and how is the overall improvement of audit quality in China?

This paper empirically studies five-year data from 2013- 2017 after the implementation of GAEIC by all A-share listed companies, first, the paper studies the regulation function of internal control and external audit on accrual and real earnings management respectively, and then further studies the concrete effect of the combination of internal and external governance mechanisms on accrual and real earnings management of enterprises.

The contribution of this paper is: ①This research divides earnings management into accrual and real earnings management, which enriches the empirical research on earnings management. ②There is a complementary relationship between internal control and external audit in restraining accrual earnings management, which also supports the conclusion of Fan Jinghua et al. (2013). Most of the articles studied the relationship between internal control and external audit on earnings management and find that there is a substitution effect between the two. The possible reasons lie in the weak internal control environment, poor sense of control and the low level of business capability of most accounting firms in China before the implementation of GAEIC in 2012. ③External audit can effectively regulate real earnings management, while internal control is invalid on real earnings management. Internal control and external audit have neither complementary nor substitution relationship in regulating real earnings management.

2. Theoretical Background and Research Hypothesis

2.1 Internal Control and Earnings Management

One of the fundamental objectives of internal control is to guarantee the quality of financial reports, hence theoretically, internal control can regulate accrual earnings management behavior of enterprises and improve the quality of accounting information of enterprises. Overall, effective internal control, as an internal governance mechanism, can regulate accrual earnings management from two paths: Firstly, controlling and monitoring activities can discourage management and other employees from deliberately misjudging the opportunity and motivation to increase accrual earnings, and can increase their implementation costs (Zhang You tang, 2017). Secondly, good internal controls can prevent unintentional, random, procedural accrual earnings errors in the information transmission process (Zhang Guoqing, 2008).

Real earnings management is a kind of earnings manipulation by management to mislead information users by arranging deviation from the normal business activities of the enterprise, such as abnormal price promotion and reduction of expenses on research and development (Roychowdhury, 2006). On the one hand, real earnings management is done through real business activities. Although it may damage the long-term value of the company, it is difficult to find such behavior in internal control because of the irregularity and secrecy. On the other hand, real earnings management activities are often carried out by the ways of abnormal price reduction and sale promotion and the reduction of research and development expenditure, among others. These ways are the most important decision of the enterprise and need cooperation between many key departments of the company; this kind of cooperation will override the internal control, and make the internal control invalid. Accordingly, we make the following assumptions:

H1a: Internal control quality is significantly negatively correlated with accrual earnings management.

H1b: Internal control quality has no effect on real earnings management.

2.2 External Audit and Earnings Management

The basic goal of an external audit is to guarantee the reliability of the financial report, so it is necessary for the CPA to find out and regulate enterprises' accrual and real earnings management behavior. In theory, the higher the audit quality in the accounting firm, the better in regulating earnings management behavior of the enterprise. There are three main reasons: ①The stronger the professional competence of the accounting firm, the better the audit quality. Its auditors are more likely to find potential accrual and real earnings management behavior because of their richer audit experience and solid professional knowledge. ②Based on the theory of reputation, accounting firms with good audit quality pay more attention to their reputation value, and if their reputation is damaged, the cost will be far greater than the loss caused by losing clients. In order to protect their reputations, auditors will be more careful in the course of their practice and be more able to bear pressure from the management of the firm, so as to better protect the interests of stakeholders. Because of the "brand effect," audit firms of good quality are more willing to expose and urge management to regulate earnings management behavior. ③High-quality audit firms will also make substantial investments in staff training, internal management control and audit methodology development. So, if it is disclosed to do low-quality audits, the losses will be even greater. In summary, high-quality audit firms have stronger professional competence and independence, and they can regulate not only the accrual earnings management of enterprises but also their real earnings management activities. Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following two consistency hypotheses:

H2A: External audit quality has a significant negative correlation with accrual earnings management.

H2B: External audit quality is significantly negatively correlated with real earnings management.

2.3 Analysis of Combined Effect of Internal Control and External Audit on Earnings Management and Research Assumptions

According to economic theory, there is a "substitution effect" between the two commodities if they can be replaced to satisfy the same desire of people. Internal control as an internal constraint mechanism and external audit as an external constraint mechanism, both of them can effectively regulate accrual earnings management, so this paper expects that there is a substitution effect between the two EM. In addition, when the internal control of the auditee unit is expected to be invalid, and in order to reduce audit risk, auditors usually increase substantive testing to ensure higher audit quality. This also proves from the practice that these two internal and external restraint mechanisms have the substitution effect in regulating the accrual earnings management behavior.

Based on the assumption H1B, this paper assumes that the internal control can't produce the governance effect on real earnings management, so there is no substitution effect. Is there a complementary effect between IC and Audit? In the course of auditing, whether the quality of internal control is good or not, the auditor will do substantive procedures, which can effectively find out the abnormal real earnings management of the enterprise. For example, one of the means by which an enterprise manipulates real earnings is abnormal price reducing to promote sales at the year-end, which can be found by the auditor to analyze the product's year-end gross profit ratio through substantive analysis procedure. So, this paper holds that external audit can effectively regulate the behavior of real earnings management no matter what the quality of internal control is, there is neither substitution effect nor complementary effect on real earnings management. Based on the above theoretical analysis, the following theoretical hypotheses are put forward:

H3A: Internal controls and external audits have substitution effects in regulating accrual-based earnings management.

H3B: External audit is not affected by the quality of internal controls in regulating real earnings management.

3. Sample Selection and Research Design

3.1 Sample Selection and Data Sources

The financial data are taken from the iFinD database of Tong Hua Shun, and the disclosure index of internal control information of listed companies in the robustness test is taken from the DIB internal control and risk management database. Considering that the Ministry of Finance, Securities Regulatory Commission (SRC), and other departments, respectively issued in 2008 and 2010 “Basic Norms for Enterprise Internal Control(BNEIC)” and “Complete Set of Guidelines for Enterprise Internal Control(CSGEIC),” the listed companies of Shanghai and Shenzhen on Main Board are required to be implemented in 2011 and 2012. In order to guarantee the quality of panel data, this paper selects all listed A-share companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen from 2013 to 2017 as research samples, excluding financial enterprises, enterprises labelled as ST or *ST, and data with insufficient observations in order to avoid extreme value effects. Finally, 12,392 value observations were obtained from 2,939 enterprises. The sample enterprises from the period of 2013 to 2017 were 2338 in 2013, 2306 in 2014, 2398 in 2015, 2589 in 2016 and 2771 in 2017.

3.2 Research Method and Design

3.2.1 Interpreted Variables

3.2.1.1 Measurement of Accrual Earnings Management

This paper adopts the relatively novel Jones model (Kothari et al., 2005) to measure the manipulated amounts of accrual earnings management. Due to the fact that the amounts may be positive or negative, we use absolute $ABSDA_{i,t}(DA_{i,t})$ representing the amount of accrual earnings management, which can avoid the offset of positive and negative amounts together. In this way the measurement result will be more accurate. The higher the value of $ABSDA_{i,t}$, the higher the degree of manipulation accrual earnings management by the enterprise.

3.2.1.2 Measurement of Real Earnings Management

Roychowdury (2006) and Zhang Jiaying (2014) suggest that manipulating sales, manipulating production and manipulating discretionary expenses are three ways to manipulate real earnings management. This paper uses the abnormal net cash flows from operating activities ($DCFO$), abnormal production costs ($DPROD$) and abnormal expenses ($DEXP$) to measure them separately. Calculation methods are the use of actual values less estimated expected values, with the difference being the abnormal amounts.

According to Cohen et al. (2010) earnings management model, the total amount of real earnings management $REM_{i,t}$ represents the difference after deducting the abnormal net cash flows and abnormal expenses from abnormal production, i.e.:

$$REM_{i,t} = DPROD_{i,t} - DCFO_{i,t} - DEXP_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

The higher the value of the REM index, the higher the degree of real earnings management.

3.3 Explanatory Variables

3.3.1 Internal Control

Signaling theory shows that enterprises with better internal control are more inclined to employ professional accounting firms to audit and publish the audit results in order to gain the favor of stakeholders. Although in China, the Ministry of Finance, in conjunction with SRC and other departments, requires listed companies to

disclose audit reports of internal control, a number of companies are unable to disclose audit reports for various reasons. Moreover, the credibility of audit reports of internal control issued by different accounting firms is different, because the better the audit quality, the more probability of the audit firm finding internal control defects, and the better the independence audit. Therefore, this paper uses the ideas of Lei Ying et al. (2013) and Hu Quying et al. (2016) to assign the internal control quality of listed companies by the following methods:

Table 1: Valuation Basis of Internal Control Quality

Internal Control Audit Report Disclosure Status		Scores	
Undisclosed Internal Control Audit Report		0	
The internal control audit report has been disclosed	Non-Standard Unreserved Opinions		
	Standard Unreserved Opinions	Audited by international BIG4	4
		Audited by local BIG8	3
		Audited by other accounting firms	2

3.3.2 External Audit

De Angelo (1981) put forward the "reputation theory." That is, the quality of the external audit is positively related to the size of audit firms. The main reason is that the size of accounting firms is in direct proportion to their professional ability and has the willingness to maintain independence. Scholars have proved the existence of reputation theory through empirical research. So, in the study of audit quality, the prevailing international practice is to set up a virtual variable, whether or not it is audited by International BIG4. In China, the top eight domestic accounting firms (Local BIG8) started late. However, the audit quality and market share are closer to BIG4 by the support of national policies and the absorption of mergers and acquisitions, although there is still a gap between the Local BIG8 and International BIG4 in comprehensive strength. Therefore, this paper still uses the valuation method to evaluate the external audit quality, as shown in the following table:

Table 2: Valuation Basis of External Audit Quality

Accounting Firm	Scores
International BIG4	3
Local BIG8	2
Others	1

3.4 Control Variables

Combining existing literature (Fan Jinghua et al., 2013; Cao Guohua et al., 2015; Zhang Youtang, 2017), the following control variables are added to the regression model: state-owned, capital concentration, institutional property, company size, asset-liability ratio, return on total assets, loss, year, industry (see table 3).

Table 3: Variable Definition Summary Table

Variable type	Code	Name	Calculation Method
Interpreted variables	ABSDA	Accrual Earnings Management	Jones Model of Performance Matching
	REM	Real Earnings Management	Refer to model (1)
Explanatory variable	IC	Internal Control	Refer to Table 1
	AUDIT	External Audit	Refer to Table 2
Control variable	STATE	State-Owned	State-owned enterprises take the value 1. Otherwise, it is 0
	CC	Capital Concentration	The proportion of the top ten shareholders
	IP	Institutional Property	Institutional investor shareholding ratio
	SIZE	Company Size	The base 10 logarithm of total assets at the end of the period
	LEV	Asset-liability Ratio	Year-end total assets / year-end total liabilities
	ROA	Return on Total Assets	Profit before interest and taxes / average total assets of the year
	LOSS	Loss	If the enterprise has a loss, the value is 1. Otherwise, it is 0.
YEAR	Year	Time dummy variable	
IND	Industry	Industry dummy variable	

4. Model Design

To verify the influence of internal control or external audit on two kinds of earnings management, the following multiple linear regression models are constructed:

$$ABSDA(or REM) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 IC + \alpha_2 Controls + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

$$ABSDA(or REM) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AUDIT + \alpha_2 Controls + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

$$ABSDA(or REM) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 IC + \alpha_2 AUDIT + \alpha_3 Controls + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

Control for the control variable set, ε is the error term. At the same time, in order to study the complementary or substitution effect between internal control and external audit, this paper uses the method of Fan Jinghua et al. (2013) to deal with internal control and external audit. All samples are divided into two groups according to the quality of internal control. The effect of external audit is analyzed on accrual and real earnings management in two groups, and then judge whether the hypotheses of H3A and H3B are established or not.

4. Results and Findings

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 4 provides descriptive statistical analysis for the main variables. From the statistical analysis, the average value of ABSDA is 0.057, while the average value of REM is -0.055. The average level of accrual earnings management of enterprises is slightly higher than that of real earnings management. In addition, the maximum value of ABSDA is 2.362, while the minimum value of REM is -7.140 and the maximum is 4.765. It shows that the upper limit of profit changes by real earnings management is far higher than accrual earnings management. The possible reason is that real earnings management is more secretive and not easy to be discovered by regulators and auditors. IC has a mean of 1.506, less than half the maximum of 4, and it shows so far that the internal control quality of listed companies in China is still at a low level. Regulators are not optimistic about the effect of the implementation of the Guidelines on the Application of Enterprise Internal Control. The mean value of Audit is 1.723, which is more than half of the highest value 3, indicating that most of the listed companies in China are audited by International BIG4 or Chinese Local BIG8.

Table 4: Undivided Group Descriptive Statistics

VARIABLES	N	mean	sd	min	Max
ABSDA	10,601	0.057	0.079	0.000	2.362
REM	11,489	-0.055	0.284	-7.140	4.765
IC	12,392	1.506	1.443	0	4
AUDIT	12,392	1.723	0.568	1	3
STATE	12,392	0.372	0.483	0	1
CC	12,392	0.575	0.152	0.013	1.012
IP	12,392	0.397	0.229	0	0.987
SIZE	12,392	5.640	0.572	2.765	8.381
ROA	12,392	0.060	0.132	-1.121	10.616
LEV	12,392	0.428	0.210	-0.195	1.636
LOSS	12,392	0.076	0.265	0	1

In order to further find out the effect of internal control and external audit on two kinds of earnings management, the other variables are divided into two groups according to the level of internal control quality for descriptive statistical analysis, this is depicted in Table 5. According to the average of internal control quality, the mean values of ABSDA and REM are respectively 0.053 and -0.038 in the sample group with good internal control. The mean values of ABSDA and REM are respectively 0.061 and -0.076 in sample groups with poor internal control levels. The mean of ABSDA for the whole sample was 0.057, while the mean of REM is -0.055. The ABSDA and REM in the high-quality internal control samples group are lower than mean with whole samples, while ABSDA and REM in the samples group with low quality internal control are higher than mean with whole samples, indicating that, internal control can restrain the degree of ABSDA and REM and regulate earnings management. In addition, the quality of external audit differed significantly between the two sample groups, the audit quality is also high with the mean of 1.781 in the high quality internal control sample groups and low with 1.654 in the sampled group with low quality internal control, indicating that, internal control and external audit may be complementary in relationship.

Table 5: Grouped Descriptive Statistics

VARIABLES	(Sample Group with Good IC)					(Sample Group with Poor IC)				
	N	mean	sd	min	max	N	mean	sd	min	max
ABSDA	5,658	0.053	0.071	0.000	2.362	4,943	0.061	0.087	0.000	2.113
REM	6,296	-0.038	0.254	-2.919	3.171	5,193	-0.076	0.316	-7.140	4.765
AUDIT	6,711	1.781	0.602	1	3	5,681	1.654	0.517	1	3
STATE	6,711	0.575	0.494	0	1	5,681	0.131	0.338	0	1
CC	6,711	0.568	0.164	0.013	1.012	5,681	0.584	0.137	0.045	0.975
IP	6,711	0.462	0.211	0	0.987	5,681	0.321	0.226	0	0.922
SIZE	6,711	5.839	0.613	2.940	8.381	5,681	5.404	0.408	2.765	7.779
ROA	6,711	0.055	0.063	-1.121	0.663	5,681	0.065	0.182	-0.599	10.62
LEV	6,711	0.487	0.207	0.010	1.636	5,681	0.359	0.190	-0.195	1.256
LOSS	6,711	0.082	0.275	0	1	5,681	0.068	0.252	0	1

4.2. Analysis of Regression Results:

4.2.1 Internal Control, External Audit and Accrual Earnings Management

As can be seen from table 6 below, the second column IC coefficient is -0.003 when internal control is considered separately. The negative correlation at the 1% level shows that the higher the quality of internal control, the lower the degree of accrual earnings management, so we accept the hypothesis H1A. In the case of the external audit alone, the third column has an Audit factor of -0.004, shows that there is a significant negative correlation at a 1% level, thereby indicating that the higher quality of external audit can also regulate the degree of accrual earnings management. Therefore, H2A is accepted. We add both internal control and external audit to formula (4), with the regression factors for IC and AUDIT been -0.002 and -0.003 respectively, as shown in column IV of table 6. It shows that there is a significant negative correlation at 1% and 5% levels respectively, indicating that both of them have to regulate the effect on accrual earnings management. But in models (2) and (3) where the internal control or external audit is a separate explanatory variable, the regression coefficient and significance correlation level in model (4) decrease slightly, which indicate that there might be substitution effect between internal control and external audit in the combined regulation of accrual earnings management.

Table 6: Internal Controls, External Audit and Accrual Earnings Management

	Model (2)	Model (3)	Model (4)
	ABSDA	ABSDA	ABSDA
IC	-0.003*** (0.001)		-0.002*** (0.001)
AUDIT		-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.003** (0.001)
STATE	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)
CC	0.021*** (0.006)	0.025*** (0.006)	0.022*** (0.006)
IP	-0.022*** (0.004)	-0.024*** (0.004)	-0.022*** (0.004)
SIZE	-0.012*** (0.002)	-0.012*** (0.002)	-0.011*** (0.002)
LEV	0.059*** (0.005)	0.058*** (0.005)	0.059*** (0.005)
ROA	0.220*** (0.015)	0.221*** (0.015)	0.220*** (0.015)
LOSS	0.036*** (0.004)	0.036*** (0.004)	0.036*** (0.004)
Year	Control	Control	Control
Industry	Control	Control	Control
_cons	0.078*** (0.011)	0.085*** (0.011)	0.079*** (0.011)
N	10601	10601	10601
R ²	0.070	0.069	0.070

Note: Standard errors in parentheses: †p < 0.2, *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01

4.2.2 Internal Control, External Audit and Real Earnings Management

As can be seen from Table 7 below, for REM, the second column takes into account the effect of internal control, and the coefficient for IC is 0.002, although positive, but not significant, hence the acceptance of hypothesis H1B, which states that internal control quality has no effect on real earnings management. Column 3 is the impact of external audit, AUDIT Regression Factor of -0.016. The negative correlation at a 1% level shows that high-quality external audits can regulate not only the accrual earnings management but also regulate its real earnings management and the empirical results support H2B. In addition, as shown in the fourth column below, when both internal control and external audit are considered in formula (4), the coefficient of Audit is -

0.018 and significantly negative at the level of 1%. The IC coefficient was 0.005 when the combined action is studied, and it is significantly positive at a 5% level. The empirical data show that, the internal control is invalid in regulating real earnings management. The possible reasons are that, real earnings management reflects the economic strength and management ability of enterprises to a certain extent, and has a positive effect on increasing accounting information content and quality. It is more secretive and can't be detected by internal control, such as the expansion of sales by relaxing credit policy or reducing price, so long as the activity does not violate the approval process of internal control, and hence internal control can't restrain it. The auditor can judge whether the sales are abnormal by implementing substantive analysis procedure and combining the macro-economic and industry development to analyze, and then regulate its real earnings management activities.

Table 7: Internal Controls, External Audit and Real Earnings Management

	Model (2)	Model (3)	Model (4)
	REM	REM	REM
IC	0.002 (0.002)		0.005** (0.002)
AUDIT		-0.016*** (0.005)	-0.018*** (0.005)
STATE	0.049*** (0.006)	0.052*** (0.006)	0.048*** (0.006)
CC	-0.039** (0.020)	-0.036* (0.020)	-0.030† (0.020)
IP	-0.074*** (0.014)	-0.071*** (0.014)	-0.075*** (0.014)
SIZE	-0.062*** (0.006)	-0.057*** (0.006)	-0.060*** (0.006)
LEV	0.292*** (0.016)	0.292*** (0.016)	0.290*** (0.016)
ROA	-0.126*** (0.020)	-0.124*** (0.020)	-0.124*** (0.020)
LOSS	0.026*** (0.010)	0.027*** (0.010)	0.026** (0.010)
Year	Control	Control	Control
Industry	Control	Control	Control
_cons	0.206*** (0.037)	0.203*** (0.036)	0.214*** (0.037)
N	11489	11489	11489
R ²	0.067	0.068	0.068

Note: Standard errors in parentheses; †p < 0.2, *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01

4.2.3 Combined Effect of Internal Control and External Audit

Using the methods of Fan Jinghua et al. (2013), this paper divides all samples into two groups according to the quality of internal control (see descriptive statistics for grouping method) in order to study the combined effect between internal control and external audit. The regression results are shown in Table 8 below. For ABSDA, in a group with good internal control quality, the external audit factor is -0.004 and significantly negative at the level of 1%, while in the group with poor internal control quality, the external audit is -0.003, but not significant. The results show that the higher internal control quality is helpful for an external audit to regulate accrual earnings management, i.e., internal control and external audit have a complementary relationship in regulating accrual earnings management, therefore, H3A is rejected as a hypothesis. The reasons may be as follows: ①Internal control (IC) regulates the accrual earnings management of the enterprise from "process supervision." External audit (EA) regulates it from "result supervision," IC and EA combine to further reduce the level of accrual earnings management in the time dimension of regulating accrual earnings management. ② the track left by effective internal control can provide audit evidence about accrual earnings management for the auditor's audit and greatly facilitate the auditor to find accrual earnings management. For REM, according to the results of grouped regression, the regression coefficients of AUDIT in both sampled groups are significantly negative. This shows that the external audit is not influenced by the quality of internal control in regulating real earnings management, i.e., there is neither substitution nor complementary effect between internal control and external audit, so we accept the hypothesis H3B. This is not consistent with the findings of Fan Jinghua et al. (2013).

Table 8: External Audit and Earnings Management after Grouping

	ABSDA		REM	
	Good IC	Poor IC	Good IC	Poor IC
AUDIT	-0.004 ^{***} (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.011 ^{**} (0.005)	-0.028 ^{***} (0.008)
STATE	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.005 [†] (0.004)	0.047 ^{***} (0.007)	0.034 ^{***} (0.013)
CC	0.021 ^{***} (0.007)	0.032 ^{***} (0.010)	0.057 ^{**} (0.024)	-0.120 ^{***} (0.034)
IP	-0.020 ^{***} (0.006)	-0.028 ^{***} (0.006)	-0.102 ^{***} (0.019)	-0.037 [*] (0.021)
SIZE	-0.015 ^{***} (0.002)	0.005 (0.004)	-0.032 ^{***} (0.007)	-0.103 ^{***} (0.013)
LEV	0.046 ^{***} (0.006)	0.063 ^{***} (0.008)	0.175 ^{***} (0.018)	0.359 ^{***} (0.027)
ROA	0.158 ^{***} (0.020)	0.248 ^{***} (0.023)	-1.115 ^{***} (0.059)	-0.044 [*] (0.023)
LOSS	0.023 ^{***} (0.004)	0.052 ^{***} (0.006)	-0.068 ^{***} (0.013)	0.031 [*] (0.018)
Year	Control	Control	Control	Control
Industry	Control	Control	Control	Control
_cons	0.084 ^{***} (0.015)	0.063 ^{***} (0.017)	0.113 ^{**} (0.047)	0.360 ^{***} (0.057)
N	5658	4943	6296	5193
R ²	0.074	0.084	0.124	0.062

4.3 Robustness Test

In order to increase the credibility of the research results, this paper uses the replacement critical variable method to test the robustness. The above-mentioned measurement of internal control quality adopts the valuation method. We choose another prevailing practice in China, which is to measure internal control quality by using the index of information disclosure of internal control of listed companies based on the key accounting research project of Dibo Company. At the same time, the above-mentioned measurement of external audit quality is also based on the accounting firm category for scoring. We then use the method of Cao Guohua et al. (2014) to measure the quality of the external audits by setting up virtual variables. If the audited entity is the International BIG4 or Chinese Local BIG8, it is 1, otherwise 0. The two explanatory variables are brought back into the regression equations, and the new regression results are almost consistent with the previous ones, so the robustness test is passed. Considering the limited space, we omit the new regression result.

5. Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper researches whether internal control and external audit, which are two aspects of internal and external governance mechanism, play a regulating role in earnings management activities respectively, which are further divided into accrual earnings management and real earnings management, and the combined effect of internal control and external audit on accrual and real earnings management respectively.

Analyzing data on the Annual Reports of Listed Companies on mainboard from 2013 to 2017 in Shanghai and Shenzhen, we find that, firstly, effective internal control can regulate accrual earnings management, but has no effect in real earnings management; Secondly, effective external audit can not only restrain accrual earnings management but also constrain real earnings management. Thirdly, internal control and external audit have a complementary relationship in regulating accrual earnings management. The higher the quality of internal control, the more helpful the external audit can play its governance role on accrual earnings management. Internal control and external audit have neither complementary nor substitution relationship in regulating real earnings management.

Based on these findings, we recommend that Internal control can play its governance role on reducing the degree of accrual earnings management, and can also promote the external audit to play its stronger governance role on accrual earnings management, the government department should further improve the construction of internal control system. As the quality of external audit plays an important role in restraining the two kinds of earnings management, government departments should continuously strengthen the audit quality of accounting firms and constantly improve their professional competence and independence in the audit process. Internal control does not promote an external audit to regulate real earnings management, accounting firms should not rely on internal control when they find that the enterprise has the motivation and signs of real earnings management.

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